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ORGANISATIONAL BEHAVIOUR
SEMESTER 1 2020/2021

REFLECTIVE REPORT

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OVERVIEW

This reflective report is regarding my first-hand experience conducting fieldwork for my master's degree. The Master of Management (MM) course in Universiti Brunei Darussalam (UBD) is normally 18 months program with the learning goals of competency in theoretical knowledge and implementation of a respective topic or field, the ability to use the analytical and strategic ideas to address business challenges, and the ability to manage multiple work environment (UBD School of Business and Economics, n.d.). As a graduate from Bachelor of Science in Mathematics, it is difficult to seek for suitable job with the Mathematics qualification. Based on experience working in finance department, it gave hard time for a non-business graduate with non-business background to fit into the business world without understanding the ideas and concepts. Therefore, it motivates me to choose MM to expand more on the knowledge and skills.

For my first semester as MM student in UBD, I enrolled in Organizational Behavior as it is one of the core modules. The module provides theoretical and analytical knowledge of organizational behavior in order to gain an understanding of the scope and future importance of organizational behavior as an area of research in today's life of organizational. According to what have the lecturer assigned us to do, it shows that the class module is mostly into an independent style of learning and more likely towards analytical knowledge than theoretical knowledge. This can be seen from the way how the lecturer provides us articles to read, timeline assigned for the module's assignments and the work assignment given such as task on *Motivations Behind Pursuing MM*.

What can I observe from the Organizational Behavior module is that manage to improve my skills in research and having a good team or friends motivates me to perform smartly in completing the task given. Other than that, I have learnt many useful and helpful information which could be applicable to my life either now or for the future. For instance, how to manage and control the business management problem according to the theoretical knowledge delivered during the class. Nevertheless, it also helps me to gain my knowledge and skills in critical thinking. Admitted also that, I personally agreed with the weekly assignment as it helps to boost my knowledge and skills, and enhance my understanding in which theoretical and analytical framework is suitable with the topic that I have assigned with. Organizational Behavior module also taught me how to be a good team member while at the same time to maintain the good relationship and friendship with my group members. To add on, the peer reviews activity is also beneficial for me as it enhanced my writing skills after reading numerous of papers.

1. THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL KNOWLEDGE

The design and presentation of the course was partly on the basis of my perception that the lecturer come to the course with a rich experience, practical knowledge, skills and qualities, about learning challenges, etc. Winkler (2001) mention that this perception id mainly practical and implicit. By practical knowledge, it formed from first-hand teaching and learning experiences, and which amounts to an understanding of what is needed for success (Winkler, 2001). Hence, by taking the Organizational Behavior module, I have encounter motivation in learning, leadership style in group assignment, as well as the importance of individual differences (team identification). Ruggieri and Abbate (2013) explained that leadership is a group characteristic that has a direct effect on the team identification. This is because team identification is one of the most influential variables in determining one's identity (Ruggieri & Abbate, 2013), thus, it reflects the perceived sense of belonging to a specific team by individual members. Identification of the team motivates members to act according to the interests of the group and enhances the relations between members. Moreover, according to Musa and Idris (2020), the youth people usually have the self-awareness and enthusiasm to develop their leadership ability. Self-awareness in this case requires recognition of one's strengths, weaknesses, and limitation (Musa & Idris, 2020), therefore by recognizing all the factors, they can identify their belongings of leadership style.

Since my Master's study is during the pandemic of COVID-19, most of the modules I took were conducted via online and I found that the online learning somehow has both pros and cons. However, having goal-setting helps me to stay motivated in my study. A broad variety of motivational theories derived from motivational studies such as the self-determination theory, expectancy-value theory, goal theory, mindset theory, and control-value theory have been commonly used to explain the conceptual and psychological factors that optimize the learning and engagement in the class (Thomas et al, 2020). Furthermore, I find it is very useful and important as a MM student to make use the knowledge that has been delivered as it is helpful for my future reference along with to enhance my personal growth.

Growth motivation is analyzed within a paradigm of eudaimonic growth and self-development as a desire for persona growth. Personal growth is commonly desired quality of life (Bauer et al, 2015), as what had been asked in one of my Organizational Behavior class, where we were given a task on what motivates us to pursue to study MM. By applying all theories that I have learn in this semester, I could say that personal growth is one of the factors that motivates me to study MM together with the Maslow's need Hierarchy theory. Maslow classifies the needs from the lowest to the highest degree of needs (self-actualization, esteem, love or belonging, safety, to physiological) (Turabik & Baskan, 2015) to maintain the valuable insight for management perspective (Ramlall, 2004).

2. INDIVIDUAL OPINIONS AND CONTRIBUTIONS ON THE GROUP ASSIGNMENT

During the almost 14 weeks of the group assignment, I had the opportunity to express my skills in doing the data analysis, statistical calculation, literature reviews, as well as finalizing the report. Furthermore, due to the first come first serve basis together with the “not so hard” kind of assigned case study topic, it is an advantage and easy for me to accomplish my work in finding the content and the data collection. Admitted also that my team is a good team in accomplishing the work assignment, although my team did not discuss or officially assigned a specific role in the group assignment but we contribute equally in finishing the task. Everyone in the group knows what to do. In addition, I also work in the formation of survey question. Overall, my job in the group is formatting, editing and finalizing the final case study report.

3. OPINIONS OF THE TEAM MEMBERS ON THE GROUP ASSIGNMENT

The group assignment was assigned with a total of four members namely Khairunissa, Muqri, Syhadah and myself. All of us were a total stranger at the beginning, however we were able to work together with complaining as we get along every discussion session either virtually or physically. As said by Khairunnisa, she thinks that I am an organize type of person in terms of doing the format of report. She also mentioned that I am the “planner” in the group. Whereas, Muqri said that I am in-charge of finalizing the report and making sure all findings and inputs are in order. Meanwhile, Syhadah commented that I always motivate the group especially herself to keep focus on every assignment, not only group assignment but also the individuals. The team once said that I am an obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) person as they realized I keep editing the format of the report. To sum up, my group member and myself feels glad that we are in the same team and look forward for the next group assignment.

4. OUTCOMES OF THE GROUP ASSIGNMENT

The outcome of the group assignment is a success as we accomplished it earlier than we expected. Taking into account that all members are totally new to each other but able to work together without any misunderstanding and disagreements was not what I have imagined, however I am glad that they are my team. In the period of doing the case study, everyone is aware of their own task in terms of time management and the quality of task management. In addition, my team also has not encountered any problem in doing and submitting the ethics application and hence this may lead us to the success in accomplishing our group assignment together with the approval from the faculty office in proceeding our research methodology. The research methodology used comparative study between local and foreign university students on the behavior and attitude towards online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. Moreover, the study finding was easily

be reach as Muqri knows lot of people both locally and foreign, and as a result my team able to do comparison and see the contrast easily.

5. *INDIVIDUAL STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES*

Based on the experience I have encountered both group and individual assignments, I believe my strengths are mostly in appreciation of listening to other's point of views and being considerate during the group meeting, also I take responsibility for any of my actions during discussion as well as doing the report. In addition, I can say that my personal strength is being able to finish the assignment earlier with being motivated in every group and individual assignments. In this way I could be a better MM student and perhaps future manager who can gives and takes not only from the MM course works also from the real-life situations.

Beside my strengths, I still have things that I would like to work on in addition to my strengths. I think that my weakness lies in adequate time management. Although I always finish my task earlier, but within the period of time in accomplishing the task I always keep distracted with the feeling of being "not in mood" situation, such as not having the mood to do the assignment, and this led to wasting my time. On the other hand, based on the individual work assignment, I figured that I am not good enough in reporting the primary source especially if it is an interview source, as I realize that I should go to more direct question rather than open-ended question. Moreover, as a Bachelor of Science in Mathematics graduate, writing a report or paper is not part of my expertise, but as I go along with the MM courses or lectures, especially Organizational Behavior, writing could be my strengths than weaknesses as we were asked to do the weekly assignments.

6. *RECOMMENDATION*

I agree that being an independent (autonomous) learner is the best way to learn which is it requires strong communication skills and discipline as what I did in my group assignment. From this module, I have improved my communication skills, writing skills, and improved my time management especially for meeting discussion and deadlines for submission. From my point of views of group assignment, a good team is a key success in pursuing MM as it may be the experiment practices before being a good manager in the future. By recognizing what type of person you are in terms of leadership style and personal identification along with recognizes your motivation is important in participating the group work. As knowing that I am autonomy leadership style, I might want to be autocratic leader at the same time, so that I can lead and to be lead with other members. Therefore, it could be very grateful for me to have a participative democratic leadership style for the next group assignment.

7. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE REFLECTIVE REPORT

Reflective report gives the ability to think more intensely about what student are doing and to learn from their experience, as states in *Genres in Academic Writing* (n.d.), also mentions that reflective report gives the chance to learn how the real-world or learning activities support the student with what they have learned in class (*Genres in Academic Writing*, n.d.). Writing down ideas makes it easy for the student to learn rather than to develop correlations between what they think, what they being told, and what they do.

From my point of view, reflective report is helpful for me to evaluate my own perception, practices, abilities or responses. In this reflective report, I can explain and objectively see my strengths and weaknesses based on the assigned task, along with recognizing what is needed to be change and improve. Therefore, as explained, my experience of being autonomous in studying to complete the tasks can be used in the future as I learnt not to focus entirely on the notes given, I also need to be more participative in accessing other sources such as newspaper, journal, articles or even the UBD library's e-resources.

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